

Investigating the effect of corrosion on reinforced concrete structure with novel encoded electromagnetic wave imaging technique

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Abstract

In reinforced concrete (RC) structures, the intricate process of corrosion significantly threatens their structural integrity. The existing non-destructive methodologies must be enhanced to elucidate the degradation of strength comprehensively. Therefore, we introduce an innovative approach involving encoded electromagnetic (EM) wave imaging. Our method involves studying the failure mechanisms across various RC beam structures exhibiting different degrees of corrosion. The smart sensor tags are affixed to the reinforcement of these structures. By subjecting the RC beam specimens to loading, we discern indicators of strength reduction by analyzing encoded EM spectrum images acquired from these smart sensor tags. This analysis employs a novel strategy called the Fourier-fractal EM-Wave imaging technique. To illustrate the effectiveness of our methodology, we constructed three distinct RC beam specimens. These specimens are equipped with a collective total of 72 smart sensor tags, with each RC beam accommodating 24 embedded smart sensors within its reinforcement framework. The results derived from our study underscore the success of the Fourier-fractal EM-Wave imaging technique in accurately identifying strength reduction attributed to corrosion-induced deterioration in reinforced concrete structures.

Keywords: Corrosion, electromagnetic wave images, Fourier-fractal, non-destructive method, reduction strength.

1. Introduction

The cornerstone of contemporary civil engineering, Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures, are gradually yet significantly compromised by the insidious corrosion process. This phenomenon predominantly results from the sustained exposure of embedded steel reinforcements to environmental elements, including moisture, oxygen, and chloride ions [1]. The invasion of these agents through the concrete's protective layer instigates a series of

corrosive reactions in the steel bars, leading to a marked degradation in their load-bearing capacity and the crucial bond shared with the surrounding concrete [2]. This silent deterioration poses a tangible threat to the safety of the structure's occupants. It inflicts substantial economic burdens stemming from the imperative repairs or replacements of the compromised structural elements [3-4].

Given this context, there is an imperative and escalating need for developing and implementing an effective non-destructive testing (NDT) technique that can accurately assess the structural integrity of RC structures in the wake of corrosion-induced damages. Over the years, several NDT techniques grounded in the principles of electromagnetic waves (EM-Wave) and Acoustic Emission (AE) have been introduced and deployed for corrosion monitoring in RC structures [5-6]. However, these techniques invariably entail substantial operational costs while delivering on their promise of reliability, leaving a void for a cost-effective yet reliable NDT solution that has yet to be addressed over the decades.

Moreover, the existing body of literature and practice does not shed light on NDT techniques from a forensic engineering standpoint, particularly those that can be employed to identify and quantify the reduction in the strength of RC structures. In response to this exigent gap in knowledge and practice, recent scholarly endeavors have brought the potential of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, underpinned by the mechanism of EM-wave backpropagation as a promising candidate for a novel NDT technique [7-8].

This study conducts a comprehensive examination and introduces a novel Fourier-Fractal technique, integrated with encoded EM-wave spectrum images, for identifying corrosion effects on RC structures. A series of loading tests were meticulously conducted, each corresponding to varying reinforcement corrosion levels to establish the proposed technique's validity and efficacy.

2. Method and experimental procedure

This study proposes a novel method for processing raw data to extract valuable information pertinent to the observed specimen. This innovative approach intricately combines Fourier Transform and Fractal Dimension as integral components of the signal processing technique applied. Specifically, the research utilizes a self-programmed algorithm that processes the raw data, subsequently generating encoded images as a result of this comprehensive analysis.

A crucial aspect of the proposed methodology is the employment of the two-dimensional Fourier transform (2D-FFT). The 2D-FFT is notably efficient in computational terms, offering a streamlined avenue for analyzing the frequency components embedded within signals.

Furthermore, this approach facilitates straightforward filtering processes, allowing for the seamless elimination or attenuation of specific frequencies within an observed image. The formulation of the 2D-FFT can be denoted as follows [9]:

$$F(u,v) = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \text{EXP} \left[\frac{-j2\pi ux}{N} \right] \sum_{y=0}^{N-1} f(x,y) \text{EXP} \left[\frac{-j2\pi vy}{N} \right] \quad (1)$$

In which u and v function as frequency indices while $F(u,v)$ is defined for u and v in the range $[0, N-1]$.

In subsequent analysis, we use fractal dimension value (D) to identify complex patterns inherent in images. The fractal value obtained with the following formula, in which, N is the counted boxes and h is the reciprocal scale:

$$D = \frac{\log(N)}{\log(h)} \quad (2)$$

Considering the various loading phases encompassed in our experiment, it is crucial to establish a comprehensive framework for deriving the fractal dimension. Thus, drawing from Equation (2), we can further articulate:

$$D_{Avg} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D_i \quad (3)$$

In the aforementioned equation, D_{Avg} denotes the average fractal dimension calculated across all specimens. The term D_i refers to the fractal dimension ascertained during each distinct loading phase, while the variable n designates the total number of loading phases executed throughout the experiment.

Figure 1(a) illustrates the detailed workflow of this study. The experiment was designed with three loading phases, each applied to different RC specimens. Data from sensors attached to each specimen was captured with an RFID reader during the loading phases and transmitted to a user interface (PC). For details on the experimental procedure, refer to Figure 1(b). Additionally, the RC specimens exhibited varying levels of reinforcement corrosion, as elaborated in Figure 1(c).

3. Result

The data obtained in this study indicated negligible performance disparity between RC-1 and RC-2, a phenomenon attributable to the minor extent of corrosion observed on RC-2's longitudinal reinforcement, which marginally affected the overall structural integrity.

Figure 1. The framework of the encoded EM-wave imaging technique in RC assessment

In contrast, RC-3 significantly diverged from the first two specimens, exhibiting elevated pitting corrosion on its transverse and longitudinal reinforcement elements. This corrosion-induced alteration resulted in a slight increase in flexural stiffness, prominently observable until the loading phase approached approximately 85% of the ultimate load (defined herein as the peak load point at approximately 60 kN). Upon surpassing this 85% threshold, RC-3 shows heightened brittleness. Details of the load and mid-span deflection correlation can be seen in Figure 2(b).

Furthermore, an analysis of maximum deflection across the specimens revealed a distinct pattern: RC-3 registered the highest maximum deflection, followed in sequence by RC-2 and RC-1. This deflection pattern aligns with the degree of corrosion observed in each specimen, with RC-3 displaying the most extensive pitting corrosion on its reinforcement elements.

To elucidate the implications of these findings, we examined the correlation between the fractal values and mechanical properties of each specimen, as detailed in Figure 2(a). The analysis shows that as the indicators of strength reduction (including deflection and failure mode) became more pronounced with increasing corrosion in the RC specimens, there was a corresponding decrease in the fractal dimension values. This correlation underscores the close relationship between the fractal dimensions in the encoded EM-wave images and the behavior of reinforced concrete structures. The details mentioned above can be seen in Table 1.

Figure 2. (a) Fractal values during specific loading phases; (b) Mechanical properties illustrated by the load-mid span deflection relationship in different RC specimens.

Table 1. Relationship Between Fractal Value of Encoded Image and Mechanical Properties of RC Structures.

Specimen	Corrosion level	Fractal value	Maximum Load (kN)	Mid-span deflection (mm)	Failure modes
RC-1	Normal	2.113	58,88	14,494	Flexural-shear
RC-2	Moderate	2.088	59,69	14,526	Flexural-shear
RC-3	Severe	2.081	59,49	15,260	Flexural

4. Conclusion

In this study, we established a robust correlation between electromagnetic (EM) wave spectra and reinforced concrete performance, highlighting this relationship's potential for practical applications. Through experimental validation and Fourier-fractal electromagnetic wave imaging techniques, we demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in assessing the condition of deteriorated concrete structures with various levels of corrosion.

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